

ЎЗБЕКИСТОН РЕСПУБЛИКАСИ
ОЛИЙ ВА ЎРТА МАХСУС ТАЪЛИМ ВАЗИРЛИГИ

ТОШКЕНТ ДАВЛАТ
ШАРҚШУНОСЛИК ИНСТИТУТИ

«ЎЗБЕКИСТОН - АФҒОНИСТОН»
ДЎСТЛИК ЖАМИЯТИ

**“АФҒОНИСТОН XX ВА XXI АСРЛАР
ЧОРРАҲАСИДА: ТАРИХИЙ, ИҚТИСОДИЙ-
ИЖТИМОЙ, СИЁСИЙ ЖИҲАТЛАРИ ВА
УНИНГ МАРКАЗИЙ ОСИЁ МАМЛАКАТЛАРИ
БИЛАН ЎЗARO МУНОСАБАТИ МАСАЛАЛАРИ”**

Халқаро илмий-амалий конференция
материаллари тўплами

(Тошкент, 2019 йил 21-22 июнь)

Тошкент-2019

“Афғонистон XX ва XXI асрлар чорраҳасида: тарихий, иқтисодий-ижтимоий, сиёсий жиҳатлари ва унинг Марказий Осиё мамлакатлари билан ўзаро муносабати масалалари” халқаро илмий-амалий конференция материаллари тўплами – Т.: ТДШИ, 2019. 428 б.

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Ушбу тўпламга Ўзбекистон Республикаси Олий ва ўрта махсус таълим вазирлигининг 2019 йил 28 февралдаги “Вазирлик тизимидаги олий таълим муассасаларида 2019 йилда ўтказиладиган илмий анжуманлар режасини тасдиқлаш тўғрисида”ги 205-сонли буйруғига биноан 2019 йил 21-22 июнь кунлари Тошкент давлат шарқшунослик институтида ўтказилган “Афғонистон XX ва XXI асрлар чорраҳасида: тарихий, иқтисодий-ижтимоий, сиёсий жиҳатлари ва унинг Марказий Осиё мамлакатлари билан ўзаро муносабати масалалари” халқаро илмий-амалий конференция материаллари киритилган.

Унда Афғонистоннинг тарихий ривожланишига бугунги кундаги қарашлар, маданий-гуманитар омилларнинг Афғонистонни ривожлантиришдаги ўрни ва аҳамияти, Ўзбекистон ва Афғонистон ҳамкорлигининг янги босқичлари, шунингдек, Афғонистон ва Марказий Осиё республикалари ўзаро муносабатлари ёритилган.

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POST-CONFLICT AFGHANISTAN: RESEARCHING WAYS TO IMPROVE THE SOCIO-ECONOMIC CONDITIONS OF BALKH PROVINCE

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According to the Diplomat during the official visit to Uzbekistan Afghan President Ashraf Ghani and President Shavkat Mirziyoyev issued a joint statement and oversaw the signing of 20 bilateral agreements geared toward strengthening cooperation in various spheres from political to trade, transport and communications to education. In addition, more than 40 export contracts worth \$500 million were signed.¹ Last two years of bilateral relations between Uzbekistan and Afghanistan show significant progress. However, because of difficult history over three decades, Afghanistan requires special studies by Uzbek scholars, which focus to evaluate social situation, possible directions of cooperation.

Afghanistan is one of the few countries in recent human history, which has suffered from conflicts largely initiated by external forces. As the current conflict in this country winds down, there are plenty of discussions around the world concerning the reasons for the conflict, the emergence of Taliban or the causes and results of the so-called GWoT.² However, there is little discussion of the ruined socio-economic infrastructure. From my point of view, stressing the geopolitical motives of the war at this stage has no practical outcome for Afghans. In fact, it may be necessary to avoid the political aspects of the war and focus on the rebuilding of the socio-economic infrastructure.

¹ Catherine Putz. Ghani and Mirziyoyev Meet, Renew Afghan-Uzbek Ties. Connectivity was at the heart of Afghan President Ashraf Ghani's visit to Uzbekistan this week. 06.12.2017. The Diplomat. Com

² Security and Governance in Post-Taliban Afghanistan: What Went Wrong and Why? Lecture of Professor N.Shahrani. Recorded October 30, 2009. Sponsored by: University of Alaska Southeast. Produced by: UAS Video Production Services. <http://www.youtube.com/watch?v=9v5JTe8DE8w>

There are many articles, reports and books on Afghanistan offering general and often repetitious information about the inability of the Afghan government to remedy the ills of corruption, poverty, child mortality, low life expectancy, infectious diseases and other socio-economic problems.³ These publications are very informative and tend to demonstrate the author's expertise; how he or she is able to deeply understand one of the poorest nations of the world. International Conferences are preferred venues for discussions of, for example, the high level of child mortality and the low level of life expectancy. These presentations and discussions are often presented by experts in particular aspects of Afghan society, experts who are often from countries that have soldiers actively fighting in/against Afghanistan. Many of these authors are from those countries, which initiated past conflicts or the current conflict. Looking at the war on one side and the poor economic conditions because of the war on the other side, a number of publications present Afghanistan less as a country with real people and a real economy and more as an experiment in geopolitics.⁴

As the current conflict winds down, what will the people of Afghanistan be left with? Now is the time to focus on this question and search for ways to rebuild the economy of the country. The following points must be considered in relation to the reconstruction of Afghanistan.

- Afghanistan is becoming a post-conflict country, which should/will be reconstructed with international assistance.
- The government is incapable of developing and implementing extended socio-economic reform without international assistance;
- Failure of the government due to wide-spread socially and economically destructive practices, which affects its efficiency;

³ Adam Pain and Jonathan Goodhand. Afghanistan: Current employment and socio-economic situation and prospects. ILO InFocus Programme on Crisis Response and Reconstruction.

⁴ Central Asia, 19th century: Afghanistan takes the stage (“What to Read on Afghanistan?” – 01). Le Monde. 25 April 2011.

- Government is not able to respond to the needs of children and the elderly, who survive only by traditional family relationships preserved in Afghan society⁵.
- In the current situation the government is incapable of developing and implementing extended socio-economic reform covering the whole country, without international assistance;
- Reliance on foreign aid exacerbates the atmosphere of dependency on executive power, which in turn becomes one of the main barriers to economic reforms;
- The ineffectiveness of public institutions prevents the proper collection of taxes and which in turn, leads to a weak budget and therefore low salaries for civil servants, which sows the seeds of corruption.

Prospects for Balkh Province. Geographically far from conflict areas, Balkh province is more accessible to implement social-economic programs for rebuilding. Security in Balkh province, provided by the international coalition on the one side and by the local leaders can create more trustful relationships between the local population and International donors to implement social programs effectively. Existence of cultivated and potentially irrigated lands which can help in implementing special programs to develop the agricultural sector. Northern provinces are more peaceful than the southern provinces and more convenient to establish educational, business training and health programs. Northern provinces are much more in need of the above mentioned programs, because socio-politically and economically they are much more undeveloped and ignored by the central government.

Publications on Afghanistan demonstrate extended international concern and engagement to rebuild the country.⁶ There are some effective

⁵ Dr. G. Rauf Roashan. Demographic Changes, Employment and Social Security Issues of Aged in South Asia Afghanistan's Case.

⁶ Hairatan-Uzbekistan Rail Project, Afghanistan. www.railway-technology.com

programs taking place in Afghanistan to reform the judicial system⁷, the social sphere⁸, the national army and police and other governmental institutions. International organizations try to sort out the real situation and take action to improve the conditions.⁹ At the same time, the high rate of unemployment, poor conditions in education and health care spheres and uncertain conditions in business require more analyses of the social, economic and relational situations in Afghanistan.

From this point of view, it is necessary studying the social-economic situation of Balkh Province, in order to develop a special U.N. socio-economic program, indicating methods and potentialities to improve conditions. For instance, there are possible directions and schemes for cooperation between Uzbek and Afghan Universities. Researches should focus to study the following:

- Social and economic indicators;
- Demographic features and ethnic maps;
- Ethnic-political situation and activity of state institutions;
- Economic activity of cities and rural areas;
- Labor market, unemployment and working conditions;
- Educational and health care systems;
- Economic potential of the province: natural resources, level of cultivation of lands, irrigation system, animal husbandry;
- Industrial indicators, potential and possibilities of attracting foreign investors;
- Possibility of improving the agricultural sphere with the potential Amudarya;
- Barriers to improve socio-economic conditions of the province;

⁷ Astri Suhrke and Kaja Borchgrevnik. Afghanistan: Justice sector reform. New Perspectives on Liberal Peacebuilding edited by Edward Newman, Roland Paris and Oliver P. Richmond. United Nations University. 2009.

⁸ Maroof, Zakia, "An Exploratory Examination of Afghan Women Socio Economic Status (SES) and Child Health Indicator" (2010). http://digitalarchive.gsu.edu/iph_theses/134

⁹ Child & bonded labor in Afghanistan's brick kilns. New Survey highlights obstacles to ending practice. Press Release, 02.07.12. http://www.ilo.org/asia/info/public/pr/WCMS_172721/lang-en/index.htm

The basis of researches has to be qualitative, with significant quantitative component. Beyond extended library work at place, some field researches should be conducted, during which interviews should be taken from different foreign experts working in Afghanistan, local business people and public officials. In addition, surveys on the prospects of the province and economic reforms should be conducted among teachers, doctors, business people and local ethnic leaders. Data analysis taken from official sources and working closely with the academic circles in Afghanistan is important for study the real situation and possible programs.

This study provides a basis for developing programs to improve the socio-economic situation, based on the specific characteristics of the province. The results of researches may provide the raw material for various interested departments of the UN and other international organizations. The studies will pave the way for the development and implementation of new socially-oriented programs of the UN and its subsidiaries. This study serves to identify the economic potential of the province and indicates the directions of its development. Uzbek entrepreneurs are interested in investing to Afghanistan and results of the research may be used to attract foreign investment to the basic and essential areas of industry, natural resources and agriculture. Neighboring countries need more information about the real situation in Afghanistan and sociological researches will serve to develop bilateral cooperation with neighboring countries. Cooperation between academic units help to identify the economic potential and possible spheres of usage of the first railway Khairaton- Mozori-Sharif.

To my understanding Afghanistan, especially northern parts of the country has full potential for cooperation with Uzbekistan. Last year Uzbekistan has opened the educational center dedicated to teaching Afghan citizens in Termez. There are full potential of economic cooperation between two countries. Today there are tens companies in Surkhandarya region with

Afghan capital. Afghan officials express their goals to use Uzbekistan as transit to export Afghan fruits to Russia¹⁰. All these ideas demonstrate enthusiasm of both countries accelerate the recovering process of Afghanistan. Profound studies of Balkh Province allow clarifying the situation and improving the quality of cooperation. On the other hand, this study will open new perspectives for academic cooperation between Universities of Balkh Province.

¹⁰ Maksim Yeniseyev. Uzbek-Afghan co-operation gets boost with planned consulate in Termez/
<http://central.asia-news.com>